

Chemistry of nitrites: contributions of P.C. Rây and some later developments

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Manuscript received 16 June 2014, accepted 19 June 2014

Abstract : A selection of Rây's main contributions to nitrite chemistry is chronicled in this article which also presents significant supportive findings of later workers, specially those of the structural type that were not accessible during Rây's time. The following activities are scrutinized in some detail: discovery and authentication of mercurous nitrite, synthesis and coordination chemistry of mercuric nitrite with nitrogen-donor (nitrite, ammonia, mono- and di-amines and certain alkaloids like nicotine) and sulfur-donor (thiols) ligands, sublimation and vapor density of ammonium nitrite, synthesis and properties of a large family of alkylammonium nitrites and finally dissociation constant and decomposition kinetics of nitrous acid.

Keywords : Mercurous nitrite, mercuric nitrite, ammonium nitrite, alkylammonium nitrite, nitrous acid.

Introduction

After his doctoral work in Edinburgh University Rây, a young man of twenty eight, joined Presidency College of Calcutta as an Assistant Professor in 1889. He continued to work here for the next twenty seven years and then in 1916 joined the new College of Science of Calcutta University as the first Palit Professor of Chemistry to begin a second innings of activity finally retiring only in 1936. We plan to write a series of critical articles highlighting his main research contributions in chemical science. The first article of this series dealing with $[R_3S][HgI_3]$ has already appeared¹. Initially teaching took much of his time and efforts but soon he found it possible to devote some attention to research. The problem that first attracted his attention was the adulteration of edible fats and oil. With the meager laboratory facilities available he was still able to carry out experiments to quantify parameters that could help in identifying adulteration. These are detailed in his first research paper from Calcutta². Better laboratory facilities became available from 1894 when the chemistry department moved to a new building. This was the harbinger of his 'renewed and redoubled activities in the field of chemical researches...'.

In Edinburgh Rây had trained himself as an inorganic chemist but with active interest in organic molecules and

reactions as well. The initial cutting edge of his research activity in Calcutta turned out to be the chemistry of nitrites and related species following the serendipitous discovery of mercurous nitrite. And this phase of his research contributions will be scrutinized in this article. Later his interest would shift to organic sulfur compounds and their metal binding and still later he would have fruitful engagements in areas such as chemical isomorphism and fluorination of organic molecules. These will be topics of future essays of this series.

A new beginning: mercurous nitrite

Discovery and sequel :

Initially Rây had taken up (in collaboration with the Geological Survey of India) the daunting task of analyzing certain rare Indian minerals hoping to discover missing elements of the Periodic Table. But before long his research took an unforeseen turn as chronicled in the opening lines of his 1896 paper³: "*Having recently had occasion to prepare mercurous nitrate by the action of dilute nitric acid in the cold on mercury, I was rather struck by the appearance of a yellow crystalline deposit.... A preliminary test proved it...to be at once a mercurous salt as well as a nitrite*". At that time much was already known about the reaction of metallic mercury with nitric

acid. Thus the metal was known to react with cold dilute and concentrated nitric acids respectively giving hydrated mercurous and mercuric *nitrates*, both colourless. Rây's observation of yellow mercurous *nitrite* straightaway added a new dimension to the area.

In the above paper³ he described details of the preparative procedure used and of the tests he performed to show the presence of nitrite and mercurous moieties in the compound he has isolated. On the basis of quantitative analytical data the compound was initially described as a monohydrate but soon this was revised to the anhydrous formulation, $\text{Hg}_2(\text{NO}_2)_2$. It was expectedly found to partially disproportionate in water to mercuric nitrite and metallic mercury. Rây drew analogy between mercurous nitrite and the well known silver nitrite. He also speculated about the possible origin of the nitrite moiety that gives rise to mercurous nitrite in nitric acid medium. Some nitrous acid might have been already present in the nitric acid used or it might have been formed via initial reduction of nitric acid by mercury itself. A German version of the mercurous nitrite work also appeared⁴ in 1896.

The chemistry of mercurous nitrite was augmented in a series of papers by Rây. Examples include its oxidation to hydrated mercurous nitrate by dilute nitric acid⁵, quantitative examination of its thermal decomposition into a complex mixture of metallic mercury, mercuric oxide, mercurous nitrate, nitric oxide and dinitrogen tetroxide with some mechanistic comments⁶ and examination of its molecular volume vis-à-vis those of silver and alkali metal⁷ and later alkaline earth metal⁸ nitrites. The reaction of ethyl iodide with mercurous nitrite like that with silver nitrite was found to afford about equal quantities of nitroethane and ethyl nitrite⁹.

At that time metal binding by nitrite was conceived to be possible either via nitrogen, M-NO_2 (*nitronic or imidic*), or via oxygen, M-ONO (*oxylic*), and upon reaction with ethyl iodide the two forms were believed to give rise to nitroethane and ethyl nitrite respectively. The simultaneous formation of both was taken to mean that the two isomeric varieties coexist in such nitrites¹⁰. Later it was found¹¹ that upon heating monoethyl sulfate salts of alkali and alkaline earth metal with sodium, potassium or barium nitrite both nitroethane and ethyl nitrite were generated. Since the above nitrites were all believed to be strictly of *oxylic* nature, only ethyl nitrite was expected.

Rây concluded that the formation of both nitroethane and ethyl nitrite meant, "it is only during the substitution of the atom of the metal by the alkyl radical that a tautomeric change takes place"¹¹.

Such activities eventually led to the opening up of the then sparsely known field of nitrites in general. He and his students tilled this field with one new result after another. The first internationally acclaimed Indian research school in chemistry thus come into being. It was firmly established once for all that as a class nitrites are far from being the unstable and fugitive substances that chemists had supposed so far. During his years in Presidency College the primary thrust area of his research became the chemistry of nitrites and seventy percent of his papers of the period in major journals belonged to this area. A few of the more important contributions will be highlighted in later sections of this article. Immediately below we recount what more others did with mercurous nitrite later.

Structure :

The structure of $\text{Hg}_2(\text{NO}_2)_2$ was first determined in 1985¹² and better refinement was achieved by another group in 1986¹³. We determined the structure in 2011 at low temperature¹⁴. The crystalline nitrite was prepared (Fig. 1) by following a procedure reported¹⁵ by Rây in

Fig. 1. Spontaneous deposition of yellow crystalline $\text{Hg}_2(\text{NO}_2)_2$ in the reaction between dilute nitric acid and metallic mercury. For details of procedure see reference 14.

1905 and later elaborated in our work¹⁴ and depicted in Fig. 1. Each of the three determinations led to the same gross structure only the refinements varied as expected.

The structure¹⁴ is shown in Fig. 2. The molecule is planar and centrosymmetric. Each Hg atom of the mercurous moiety is unsymmetrically bonded to two oxygen atoms of a nitrite ion generating a four-membered chelate

Fig. 2. The structure of $\text{Hg}_2(\text{NO}_2)_2$.

ring. The Hg-Hg distance is 2.540(3) Å and the shorter and longer Hg-O distances are 2.201(13) Å and 2.613(13) Å respectively. Longer intermolecular Hg---O contacts (2.84–2.93 Å) are present in the crystal lattice such that every oxygen atom is linked to two mercury atoms belonging to two different molecules¹⁴.

When mercurous nitrite, wet with mother liquor is left in air it slowly gets transformed (nitrous odor is discernible) into a stable white crystalline solid within a week (~31 °C) as shown in Fig. 3. We found its composition to correspond to the hitherto unknown basic salt of

Fig. 3. Crystalline dry $\text{Hg}_2(\text{NO}_2)_2$ (left) and $(\text{Hg}_2)_3(\text{OH})_2(\text{NO}_3)_4$ (right).

formula $(\text{Hg}_2)_3(\text{OH})_2(\text{NO}_3)_4$. Structure determination¹⁴ showed it to consist of three mercurous entities connected by two Hg-O-Hg bridges, the oxygen atoms belonging to two hydroxyl groups (Fig. 4). The structures of two other basic mercurous nitrates are already known: $(\text{Hg}_2)_2(\text{OH})(\text{NO}_3)_3$ ^{16,17} and $(\text{Hg}_2)_5(\text{OH})_4(\text{NO}_3)_6$ ^{17,18}. The hydroxy-mercurous chains in the three compounds belong to the homologous series $\text{Hg}_2\{(\text{OH})\text{Hg}_2\}_n^{(n+2)+}$ ($n = 1$ ^{16,17}, 2 ¹⁴ and 4 ^{17,18}). The $n = 4$ compound has been known for long as Mariagnac's salt, formulated as

Fig. 4. Structure of $(\text{Hg}_2)_3(\text{OH})_2(\text{NO}_3)_4$.

$3\text{Hg}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{Hg}_2(\text{OH})_2$. The $n = 0$ case represents normal mercurous nitrate which is well known.

Setting the record straight :

Rây's work on mercurous nitrite raised a lot of interest and it continues to do so. The discovery was immediately noticed by *Nature* magazine which wrote in 1896, "...a paper by Dr. P. C. Ray of the Presidency College, Calcutta, on mercurous nitrite, that is worthy of note...." As seen above single crystals were grown and X-ray structure of the molecule determined and reported by three groups of workers in three different parts of the world at three different times¹²⁻¹⁴. In a recent paper¹⁹ dealing with the possible binding of mercurous and mercuric nitrites to a crown ether two^{5,15} of Rây's works on mercurous nitrite got highlighted.

In 1966, a paper²⁰ dealing with the stability of mercurous compounds reported that attempted preparation of mercurous nitrite by Prafulla Chandra's method as elaborated in his 1897 paper⁵ did yield yellow crystals as described but they slowly decomposed leaving a solid which the authors did not identify, neither did they proceed any further with the yellow crystals. Actually mercurous nitrite crystals when carefully freed from the mother liquor and dried are indefinitely stable. Otherwise they slowly get converted to a white basic salt. Rây had already noted this in his first paper³ on mercurous nitrite and we have structurally characterized the basic salt¹⁴. Thus the above noted work²⁰ tells nothing new about mercurous nitrite. Yet as late as the second half of 2011 one author²¹ cited this inconsequential paper to support *his own preconceived fiction* that mercurous nitrite does not exist!

Mercuric Nitrite

Synthesis and reactions :

One of the first few reactions of mercurous nitrite that Rây observed was its facile disproportionation in water:

$\text{Hg}_2(\text{NO}_2)_2 \rightarrow \text{Hg}(\text{NO}_2)_2 + \text{Hg}$. This reaction was however found unsuitable for preparing pure mercuric nitrite. Finally in 1904 Rây succeeded²² in achieving this goal via double decomposition between mercuric chloride and silver nitrite in aqueous media. The light yellow needles of mercuric nitrite were unstable even in dry atmosphere, very unlike mercurous nitrite which is indefinitely stable under similar conditions. Even on mild heating it promptly decomposed into mercurous nitrate and nitric oxide : $4\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_2)_2 \rightarrow 2\text{Hg}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 + 4\text{NO}$. However, its reactions with various ligands generated a panorama of coordination chemistry. We present below selected instances along with clarifications specially on the structural side that became available only much later.

Double nitrites :

Double nitrites of mercuric nitrite with sodium and potassium nitrites had been reported earlier by others as products of reactions of concentrated solutions of the latter nitrites with mercuric nitrate. Rây isolated a more extended series of crystalline double nitrites by reacting mercurous nitrite (which furnished mercuric nitrite *in situ* via disproportionation) with alkali metal nitrites in aqueous media followed by removal of the precipitated mercury and concentration of the filtrate²³. Later he similarly prepared double nitrites with calcium, strontium and barium nitrites²⁴ and with alkylammonium nitrites²⁵. Unlike mercuric nitrite itself its double nitrites are stable and solutions prepared as above, particularly that of sodium mercuric nitrite, $\text{Na}_2[\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_2)_4]$ was conveniently used by Rây as a starting material for exploring the reactions of mercuric nitrite.

The corresponding potassium salt, $\text{K}_2[\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_2)_4]$ had been well known²⁴ and from electrical conductivity data Rây later concluded that in dilute aqueous solution the complex anion dissociates into mercuric and nitrite ions²⁶. In this context we note that from around 1912 Rây started

systematically using solution electrical conductivity measurements to decipher electrolytic nature of substances. One of the first tasks he undertook was the determination of the equivalent conductivity and ionization of nitrites including a large number of metal and alkylammonium nitrites²⁷. Earlier he had reported on the ionization of nitrites as determined by cryoscopy²⁸. To complete the $\text{K}_2[\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_2)_4]$ story, infrared data collected nearly sixty years after Rây's conductivity work²⁶ suggested that in the solid state the nitrite ions are coordinated to the mercury atom probably via oxygen atoms²⁹. X-ray crystallography finally authenticated the presence of the $[\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_2)_4]^{2-}$ ion in a closely related salt³⁰. Each nitrite group is chelated to the metal via the two oxygen atoms as shown in **1a**, the Hg-O distances lying in the range 2.34-2.58 Å. The eight-coordinated anion has distorted square antiprismatic geometry as in **1b**³⁰.

Complexes of amines, alkaloids and ammonia :

In 1912 Rây reported^{31,32} the isolation of what he called additive compounds of mercuric nitrite with monoamines as well as with ethylenediamine (en). In the case of $[\text{Hg}(\text{en})(\text{NO}_2)_2]$ electrical conductivity data³² in aqueous solution showed it to be a 1 : 2 electrolyte which he interpreted by writing it as $[\text{Hg}(\text{en})](\text{NO}_2)_2$. Work done nearly fifty years later³³ which made no mention of Rây's paper³² showed that in organic solvents like nitrobenzene the compound is nonelectrolytic, $[\text{Hg}(\text{en})(\text{NO}_2)_2]$. The X-ray structure of $[\text{Hg}(\text{en})(\text{NO}_2)_2]$ itself is not known but that of the bipyridine (bpy) analogue, $[\text{Hg}(\text{bpy})(\text{NO}_2)_2]$ is³⁴ where both bpy and nitrites are chelated defining a distorted octahedral HgO_4N_2 coordination

sphere as in **2** (Hg-O, 2.32 and 2.53 Å). It is probable that Prafulla Chandra's $[\text{Hg}(\text{en})(\text{NO}_2)_2]$ has a similar structure which remains in tact in nitrobenzene solution³³ but undergoes hydration and partial dissociation³² in water.

The amine-Hg(NO₂)₂ work was extended later to include alkaloids like nicotine (**3a**), quinine etc. as amine ligands³⁵. The nicotine complex was formulated as [Hg(nicotine)(NO₂)₂]. Its structure is not known but that of [Hg(nicotine)Cl₂] is³⁶. Here each metal atom is bonded

to two chloride ligands and to two nitrogen atoms into a distorted tetrahedral geometry. One of the two nitrogen atoms is of pyridine type and the other pyrrolidine type and they come from different molecules. In effect the nicotine ligand bridges different mercury atoms creating polymeric chains as schematically depicted in **3b**. Extending the logic of nitrite chelation as observed above in [Hg(NO₂)₄]²⁻ and presumably in [Hg(en)(NO₂)₂], it is possible that Rây's [Hg(nicotine)(NO₂)₂] might have a structure similar to the chloride analogue but with the chlorides replaced by oxygen bonded nitrites. If the nitrites are indeed chelated to the metal, the coordination sphere would be distorted octahedral HgN₂O₄. On the other hand if nitrites are monodentate (N-bonded or O-bonded) the structure could be similar to **3b**.

Preceding the amine work Rây had scrutinized the case of ammonia. By reacting sodium mercuric nitrite with dilute ammonia he isolated a pale yellow salt formulated^{37,38} as a hemihydrate of Hg₂N(NO₂). He studied its thermal decomposition and reaction with ethyl iodide^{39,40}. More importantly, he converted it to compounds of the general type Hg₂N(X) via reaction with the acid HX (X = Cl, Br, NO₃, 1/2SO₄, H₂PO₄) and speculated about their structural nature^{37,38,41}. Several Hg₂N(X) type of compounds had been known for long as products of salt formation between HX and dihydrated Hg₂N(OH) (Millon's base). Rây's work provided a new synthetic route to Hg₂N(X) via the nitrite salt.

The structure of this family started emerging only around 1950 via application of X-ray diffraction and other tools. They have framework structures constituted of connected NHg₄ tetrahedra similar to the SiO₄ tetrahedra in silica. Each Hg atom in turn is shared between two nitridic

N atoms (linear HgN₂ fragment) and thus the net stoichiometry of the framework is Hg₂N and this formula unit carries a charge of 1+. The anions lying in the holes (the water molecules also reside there) of the network coordinate weakly (as in the nitrate; the nitrite may be similar) or strongly (as in halides) to the Hg atoms of the framework giving rise to different lattice types like cubic and hexagonal^{42,43}.

Thiolatomercuric Nitrites

Synthesis and reaction with alkyl iodide :

The reaction of simple aliphatic thiols (RSH) with mercuric nitrite (in the form of sodium mercuric nitrite solution) afforded the crystalline thiolatomercuric nitrite complex RSHgNO₂, described by Rây as mercury mercaptide nitrite^{44,45}. It constituted a new thiolato family of mercury that was closely akin to the known thiolato-mercuric halides RSHgX and related species some of which have been structurally characterized revealing polymeric nature.

Relevant for RSHgNO₂, is the structure of the acetate complex MeSHg(O₂CMe) in which each metal atom of the (-Hg-SMe-)_n chain is chelated to one acetate ligand which additionally interlinks the chains as depicted in **4**⁴⁶. Since the four-membered O,O-chelation by acetate is similar to that by nitrite, we suspect that MeSHgNO₂ may have a similar structure.

The reaction of RSHgNO₂ with alkyl iodides (RI) afforded a mixture of nitroalkane and alkyl nitrite and a yellow crystalline solid which Rây later (1930) showed to be the sulfonium salt [R₃S][HgI₃]. This represents an important class of coordination compounds⁴⁷ as elaborated in our previous paper on Rây's contributions to chemical research¹.

Ammonium and alkylammonium nitrites

Ammonium nitrite: sublimation and vapour density :

Ammonium nitrite had long been known as a crystalline hygroscopic solid produced by the reaction between nitrous anhydride (N_2O_3 or $\text{NO} + \text{NO}_2$) and ammonia or more conveniently between silver nitrite and ammonium chloride. It decomposed even on moderate heating to nitrogen and water: $\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_2 \rightarrow \text{N}_2 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Later it was shown that a second decomposition route affording ammonium nitrate, nitric oxide, ammonia and water also make a small contribution: $3\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_2 \rightarrow \text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3 + 2\text{NO} + 2\text{NH}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$. Initially Rây became interested in ammonium nitrite thinking that it might provide a route for direct synthesis of hydrazine, N_2H_4 , via a bimolecular decomposition route⁴⁸. Although this could not be realized, his work unfolded other features of fundamental significance in the chemistry of ammonium salts in general and of the nitrite in particular.

He demonstrated that on careful heating to 70 °C in moderate vacuum, ammonium nitrite indeed decomposes by the two routes noted above but only partly; the rest sublimes unchanged and deposits in crystalline form in cooler parts of the vessel⁴⁸. Later the sublimation of ammonium nitrite was achieved on a larger scale by others⁴⁹ trained by Rây. The sublimation work⁴⁸ prompted him to determine the vapour density of ammonium nitrite using the Hofmann apparatus⁵⁰. Meticulous corrections were applied for the gases present in the vapour due to the parallel decomposition reactions.

The corrected density, averaged over a large number of independent determinations, was 33.5. The calculated value for undissociated NH_4NO_2 is 32.0. Considering the complexity of the experiment, the agreement was indeed very satisfactory. It was thus demonstrated that NH_4NO_2 remains in undissociated molecular form (ion-pair form in today's language) in the vapour. At that time only NH_4Cl was known to behave in this manner. Later Rây determined the vapour densities of ammonium nitrate, benzoate and acetate using a different experimental setup because a much higher temperature was required. In all three cases only dissociated entities constituted the vapour⁵¹. The ammonium nitrite work⁵⁰ which he also presented at the Chemical Society in London in 1912 attracted much attention and *Nature* magazine remarked, "Prof. P. C. Ray has added to his success in preparing

ammonium nitrite in a tangible form, a further accomplishment in determining the vapour density of this very fugitive compound".

Alkylammonium nitrites :

The varied reactions of different amine types – primary, secondary and tertiary of aliphatic and aromatic families---with nitrous acid in acidic media (sodium nitrite plus hydrochloric acid) were well known in the later half of nineteenth century. But very little had been documented about the nature and properties of the nitrite salts of amines i.e. aminium nitrites. While in the midst of the ammonium nitrite work, this prompted Rây to explore and develop the chemistry of aliphatic aminium nitrites i.e. alkylammonium nitrites: $\text{R}_n\text{H}_{4-n}\text{NO}_2$ ($n = 1-3$; R = Me, Et, Pr, benzyl)⁵²⁻⁵⁸. These were generally prepared by a method analogous to that used for ammonium nitrite, i.e. by reacting amine hydrochlorides with silver nitrite. In most cases the parent amines required for making the hydrochlorides were not available in the country and the first task was to prepare them in pure form. The ethyl-, propyl-, dimethyl- and tripropyl-ammonium nitrites were isolated as viscous liquids; the rest were crystalline solids. Other nitrites reported include allylammonium nitrite⁵⁹ a thick brownish liquid and nitrosopiperazinium nitrite⁶⁰, a soft green solid.

In terms of thermal stability the benzyl series⁵⁷ was the best and the methyl series^{52,53} the worst where every member dissociated/decomposed even at room temperature. The diethyl, triethyl, dipropyl, benzyl and dibenzyl compounds could be sublimed but with varying degrees of decomposition. The thermal decomposition reactions $\text{RNH}_3\text{NO}_2 \rightarrow \text{N}_2 + \text{ROH} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{R}_2\text{NH}_2\text{NO}_2 \rightarrow \text{R}_2\text{NNO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ are essentially the same as those that occur between the corresponding amines and nitrous acid. In the trialkyl series the ethyl compound was reasonably stable but the methyl and propyl compounds dissociated readily into the corresponding amines and nitrous acid which led to secondary reactions finally affording nitric oxide, water and the respective amine and amine nitrate^{53,55,56}.

Nitrous acid

After moving to College of Science Rây published two papers in 1917 bearing the names of both Presidency College and College of Science: one on the synthesis and

thermal decomposition of cadmium and zinc nitrites⁶¹ and the other on alkaloidal derivatives of mercuric nitrite³⁵, *vide supra*. In the same year the first paper solely from College of Science appeared dealing with the parent acid of the nitrite family which had engaged him so long. We close this essay by briefly looking at it⁶². It dealt with the dissociation constant and rate of decomposition of the acid. The dissociation constant determined from electrical conductivity data was found to be 6×10^{-4} which corresponds to a pKa of 3.22, a value which has remained more or less unchanged over the decades⁶³. The decomposition of nitrous acid (HNO₃, NO and H₂O among products) has been the subject of numerous later studies including very recent ones. Rây determined the rate considering the process as pseudo-first order. The actual rate law is somewhat complicated and the mechanism of decomposition rather involved⁶⁴.

Concluding remarks

In a nutshell Rây's seminal contributions to nitrite chemistry pertain to two arenas: mercury (monovalent/bivalent) nitrites and ammonium (unsubstituted/substituted) nitrites. Discovery and authentication of mercurous nitrite, coordination chemistry of mercuric nitrite, observation of intact ammonium nitrite in the vapour phase and realization of the R_nH_{4-n}NO₂ (n =1-3) family were the high points.

Synthesis of interesting new compounds was the forte of Rây's research activity. Tools for characterization were elemental analysis, application of heat (leading to decomposition/dissociation/vaporization etc.) and reactions in solution. Later, rudimentary physical tools for determination of molecular weight (cryoscopy) and of solution ionic conductance were set up. Structure revealing tools were yet two or three decades away and guesswork had to play a major role. This greatly handicapped inorganic chemists of the time. It is a tribute to Rây's way of doing chemistry that his nitrite work all done in that era stood the test of time in an exemplary manner.

Acknowledgement

Support received from Tata Chemicals Limited in the form a distinguished emeritus professorship (2014-2016) is acknowledged.

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